

Understanding inter-farm inequalities in extreme weather event impacts: Insights from the Dutch agricultural sector

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ABSTRACT

As a result of global climate change, extreme weather events are becoming more frequent and intense. Susceptibility to extreme weather events (EWEs) is high in the agricultural sector, as these extremes can cause a decline in yields and revenue for farmers. To provide insight into ways to reduce the impacts of EWEs, this study assessed which factors explain the differences in the impacts of past weather extremes between Dutch arable farms. A survey was conducted among potato and onion farmers in the Netherlands to collect information on the past impacts of EWEs between 2018 and 2022 and the vulnerability of farmers (N = 81). The survey results showed that EWEs have already had a strong effect on farm revenues, but the extent of the impacts varied among farms. By coupling the survey data to meteorological data on EWEs, it was found that dry summers, wet fields during harvest and plowing, and warm winters were the extremes that best explained the more detrimental impacts of extreme weather amongst respondents. Additionally, differences in the physical and social vulnerability of farmers played a significant role in the observed inter-farm inequalities in impacts. Farm practices that reduce physical vulnerability are frequently inaccessible to smaller-scale or younger farmers. Further research is needed to understand the access barriers faced by these farmers. Further, future research and policies targeting the Dutch agricultural sector should no longer ignore social vulnerability factors to avoid exacerbating inter-farm inequalities, as the impacts of EWEs increase due to climate change.

1. Introduction

Global food production is negatively affected by climate change [1–3] and extreme weather events in particular [4,5]. Extreme weather events (EWEs), such as heatwaves, droughts, hailstorms, and heavy precipitation, can lead to declines in crop yields [5–10], loss of livestock [11,12], and reduced health of agricultural workers [13,14]. EWEs are projected to become more frequent and intense globally as a result of climate change [1], thereby aggravating their potential impacts on the agricultural sector [15]. The effects are more adverse in lower latitudes [1,3,5,16], with higher latitudes also experiencing positive effects from climate change (CC) such as longer growing seasons and carbon dioxide fertilization effects [17–19]. However, EWEs can outweigh these positive effects, as is projected to be the case for the Netherlands [18,19]. Weather extremes have already led to crop and financial losses for Dutch farmers [20–23], and the frequency of extreme rainfall, extreme heat, and drought events has already increased in the country [20,21,24,25] and will likely continue to increase due to CC [26–28].

Past EWE impacts were not equally distributed across the country, with farmers in Zeeland, a province in the southwestern part of

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the Netherlands, being particularly affected by the severe drought of 2018 [23] (see Appendix A for a map of the Netherlands). Future impacts of CC and EWEs are projected to be the highest in the northeastern part of the Netherlands [29]. These studies only accounted for geographical differences in extreme weather occurrence and implementation of adaptation practices. While geography and agricultural management are important determinants of EWE impact magnitude [3,30,31], impacts also depend on crop type [5, 32–35] and socio-economic farm characteristics [14,36,37]. Further, adaptation management is influenced by social and psychological factors such as risk perception of CC and cultural norms [38–40], factors that are commonly excluded from agricultural adaptation assessments [41]. At a national level, it has been assessed for the Netherlands which EWEs have the most effect on arable crop production in the current and in future climates and which crops are the most sensitive to CC [18,19], however, a desktop review revealed no studies that assessed the differences in impacts at a farm-level in the Netherlands and incorporated a social vulnerability perspective. Social vulnerability refers to characteristics of farm owners or their household that either make them more or less susceptible to the impacts of EWEs (Section 2). Social vulnerability is a frequently overlooked component in risk and vulnerability assessments, due to the difficulty of measuring it [42,43]. As a result of this exclusion, there has not been sufficient consideration for the inequality between farms and farmers regarding impacts and vulnerability, thereby limiting the understanding of the main reasons behind inter-farm differences in EWE impacts and best practices for reducing future risk of EWEs.

In the international literature on this topic, indicators are a commonly used method to assess the inter-farm differences in social and physical vulnerability to EWEs (e.g. Refs. [36,44–47]). However, these studies mostly focus on smallholder farming systems, meaning these vulnerability indicators are less applicable to the Dutch context with a very intensified agricultural system. Moreover, indicator-selection is prone to bias, as often no theoretical framework supporting the assumptions underlying the vulnerability indicators is provided [48], and validation of the indicators is often absent [49]. Empirical assessments of vulnerability are hence preferred over indices [50], but this empirical evidence is currently lacking. To address these research gaps, this study assesses the relevance of commonly used social and physical vulnerability indicators in explaining farm-level impacts of EWEs empirically, by analyzing the past impacts of EWEs in the Dutch arable farming sector. This is done by answering the research question: *What factors explain the variability in the farm-level impact of extreme weather events on arable crop production in the Netherlands?*

To answer this overarching research question, this study addresses three major research objectives: i) Quantify past impacts of EWEs on arable farmers in the Netherlands; ii) Examine in which parts of the Netherlands extreme weather events have the strongest impact on arable crop production; iii) Analyze which extreme weather events and which social and physical vulnerability indicators explain the variance in farm revenue impacts.

This was researched using an online survey. The survey was sent by email to potato and onion farmers across the country. These two crops were selected because they are among the most vulnerable crops in the Netherlands [18,19]. The survey asked farmers about past impacts of extreme weather on their farm revenue, as well as questions about their farm practices and other proxies for vulnerability (for more information, see Section 2.1). By linking the survey data to meteorological data from the Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute (KNMI), further described in Section 2.2, the relative importance of vulnerability and EWE occurrence in explaining inter-farm variance could be analyzed (Section 2.3).

2. Methodology

To analyze the past impacts of EWEs on the Dutch agricultural sector, impact is defined as a function of hazard, exposure and vulnerability (based on [51,52]). Hazard refers to EWE characteristics such as intensity and frequency. Exposure refers to the arable land used for total crop production, and acreage per crop. Vulnerability refers here to the likelihood of farmers sustaining impacts from an extreme event [53]. A distinction is made between social and physical vulnerability, where social vulnerability refers to characteristics of the farm owner, or household of the farm owner, and physical vulnerability to farm practices and characteristics.

Agricultural impact can either be defined as losses in crop yield or as losses in revenue. The chosen definition affects the relative contribution of different EWEs to total impact. When defined as crop yield losses, the impact of drought might be overestimated and impact of heatwaves underestimated. Drought yield reductions lead to minimal changes in total farm revenue, due to higher farm-gate prices when demand remains unchanged, whereas heatwaves have little effect on crop yields but reduce revenue through reduced crop quality [19,54].¹ Hence, impact is defined here as the difference between projected revenue and actual revenue attributed to EWEs, rather than changes in crop yields. This is measured as relative losses rather than absolute losses, to avoid undervaluing the impacts of smaller-scale farmers. The exposure variables, are hence no longer a required element in the impact definition, but these variables are included as vulnerability indicators, since farm size is commonly used as a vulnerability indicator [46,55].

2.1. Farmer survey

2.1.1. Data collection

An online survey was created to collect data on agricultural impacts and vulnerability. The survey was distributed in March 2023 to all 131 departments of the Netherlands Agricultural and Horticultural Association (LTO), a trade association for agricultural entrepreneurs and employers in the Netherlands. These departments were asked to share the survey with all farmers in their department cultivating potatoes and/or seed onions. Potato and seed onion were chosen because, out of the studied crops in the Netherlands, they are the most sensitive to EWEs [18,19]. The survey distinguished between seed potatoes on the one hand and ware and starch potatoes on the other, because their vulnerable periods to extremes differ [54]. Respondents were asked to indicate which of these three crops

¹ Heatwaves can cause second-growth in potatoes. This refers to a too-high growth rate, which causes tuber malformations [54].

they cultivated at least once between 2018 and 2022 and to answer questions about those crops. Data were collected for the 2018–2022 period instead of for one year, to increase the number of observations in the dataset and thus increase the reliability of the assessment.

Out of the 172 collected responses, 81 responses were retained in the dataset. The remaining 91 were discarded because the respondent did not give consent ($n = 15$), did not indicate that they cultivated potatoes or seed onions between 2018 and 2022 ($n = 15$); did not answer the impact question(s) ($n = 46$), or did not fill in their postal code ($n = 15$). The response rate per LTO department varies between 0.0 and 50.0 %, with an average of 7.5 %. This response rate is lower than for comparable email surveys conducted among farmers in the southwest of the Netherlands (9.0 %: [56,57]; 10.0–22.6 %: [21]), which could be because many LTO departments distributed the survey to all arable farmers in their department, not just potato and onion farmers. Out of the 81 respondents, 23 cultivated seed potatoes, 67 ware and/or starch potatoes, and 49 cultivated seed onions at least once between 2018 and 2022.

Potatoes and seed onions are grown in all twelve Dutch provinces [58]. However, there were no survey responses from the provinces of Gelderland, Limburg, Flevoland, and Utrecht. In the latter three, no LTO departments distributed the survey, and only one department in Gelderland distributed it. Fig. 1 depicts the number of arable farms per municipality and the respondents per municipality. The survey is representative for the north of Groningen, Zeeland, the western side of Noord-Brabant, and Zuid-Holland, but not for the rest of the country, particularly Flevoland. Further, smaller farmers (<50 ha) seem to be underrepresented in the sample, whereas farms between 100 and 150 ha are slightly overrepresented (Table A1, Appendix A). People with a more practical educational background appear to be underrepresented in this sample when compared to the average Dutch population [59].

2.1.2. Survey design

Survey participants were asked to: i) quantify, in percentages, how much total farm revenue deviated from projected revenue as a result of EWEs; ii) provide their farm's postal code; iii) indicate which extremes they perceive to have the greatest impact on crop cultivation at their farm; and (iv) answer questions about the acreage used for potato and seed onion cultivation, farm characteristics, adaptation practices, and demographics, as control variables and proxies for vulnerability.

The vulnerability indicators used in the survey were selected from previous risk and vulnerability assessments [36,44–46,63–72]. Adaptation practices that were not considered in these assessments but are reported to reduce the impacts of EWEs were included as well, as additional indicators for physical vulnerability [19,73–78].

The survey questions on obtained impacts were asked separately for each year between 2018 and 2022. Most social vulnerability questions were asked only once, except for the questions on crop insurance and exposure. For the variable 'age', data were manually transformed into time-series data, while for the other social vulnerability questions data were assumed to be constant over the five-year study period. The categories for educational attainment are based on those used by Statistics Netherlands; they categorize educational attainment into three, five, and eight levels respectively [59]. The three level aggregation is used in this study as it correlated most strongly to impacts.² Most physical vulnerability questions were asked for each year separately. For the questions regarding adaptation practices, respondents were asked to select the year they first implemented a measure and were assumed to have continued using it in subsequent years. An exception was made for the practice of applying sprout inhibitor because the sprout inhibitor chlorpropham was banned in the EU in July 2020 [79], as well as for irrigation and pesticide spraying. For these latter two adaptation measures, farmers were asked in which years they were unable to apply these practices, as the use of these adaptation measures can be hampered by EWEs (e.g. Refs. [80,81]). Appendix B contains an overview of the vulnerability questions and the distribution of the data. Because for many adaptation measures, the uptake was low, the adaptation measures were also clustered into more overarching strategies (e.g., extreme heat adaptation, improved drainage, soil quality improvement); see Appendix B for these categories.

2.2. Extreme weather: meteorological data

The KNMI provides daily precipitation and temperature data for the Netherlands with large spatial coverage [82–84]. Daily maximum and average temperature data from January 1st, 2018 until December 31st, 2022 are available for 34 locations, as are daily precipitation data for 312 locations (Figure A1 Appendix A). There were a few days of missing observations at five temperature stations, which were imputed using an auto ARIMA (autoregressive integrated moving average) model.

Weather extremes can either be defined by using a statistical approach based on percentile value, standard deviation, or return interval, or by setting a threshold temperature or precipitation value [85]. This study uses the latter approach, adhering to the meteorological definitions of EWEs identified by Schaap et al. [19,54] as the most detrimental to potato and seed onion cultivation (Table 1). The thresholds for these extremes are based on expert judgments and average farm conditions in the north of the Netherlands [81]; it is assumed that these thresholds and extremes apply to the entire country. Both temperature and precipitation extremes are included. We thereby take a more comprehensive approach compared to previous analyses of potato yield variations in the Netherlands, which only included precipitation extremes [22,23], even though temperature extremes have a more detrimental effect on crop production than precipitation extremes on a European and global scale [5].

² The three classes are based on the Dutch educational system. First level (practical education): primary school, four year practical high-school degree, completed three-years of more theoretical high school, or level one intermediate vocational education degree. Second level (moderate theoretical education): theoretical high school education degree (five or six years); level two, three or four intermediate vocational education. Third level (theoretical education): university of applied sciences or university degree.

Fig. 1. Geographical representativeness of survey respondents. A) Number of arable farms per municipality; B) Number of respondents per municipality. The map is made in QGIS [60]. Data sources: [61,62].

Table 1

Meteorological definitions and vulnerable periods of the extreme weather events affecting potato and seed onion cultivation based on the assessments made by Schaap et al. [19,54] and De Wit et al. [73].

Extreme	Crop ^a	Definition ^b	Vulnerable period
Drought spring	Onion	At least 30 consecutive days with less than five mm rainfall per day	Feb–Apr
Drought summer	Onion	At least 30 consecutive days with less than ten mm rainfall per day	Jun–Jul
Extreme heat	Seed potato	Temperature of 40 °C or higher for at least two consecutive days	Jun–Aug
	W&S potato		Jun–Sep
Extreme rainfall	Potato	At least 45 mm rainfall in a day or at least 60 mm in a period of three days	May–Sep
Extreme rainfall	Onion	At least 45 mm rainfall in one day	Jul–Aug
Late frost	Potato	Maximum temperature below –2 °C for at least two consecutive days	Apr–May
Heat wave	Potato	At least five consecutive days with a temperature ≥ 25 °C, of which at minimum three days have a temperature ≥ 30 °C	Jul–Sep
Prolonged wet period	Seed potato	More than 0.5 mm of rainfall on at least 75 % of the days in a period of at least 21 days	Jun–Sep
	W&S Potato		May–Aug
Warm and wet	Potato	Maximum temperature over 20 °C for at least 14 days, and at least 0.5 mm of rainfall on half of these days	Jul–Sep
	Onion		Jun–Aug
Warm winter	Potato	Maximum temperature over 10 °C for at least 14 days	Dec–Mar
Wet field harvest	Potato	More than 0.5 mm of rainfall on at least 75 % of the days in a period of 21 days	Aug–Oct
Wet field plowing	Potato	More than 0.5 mm of rainfall on at least 75 % of the days in a period of 21 days	Oct–Mar
Wet field	Onion	At least 45 mm rainfall in a day or at least 100 mm of rainfall in a period of eight days	Sep–Oct

^a W&S stands for ware and starch.

^b mm stands for millimeters.

The frequency of these extremes during the vulnerable period of potato and seed onion crops (Table 1) is calculated for each year between 2018 and 2022 for all temperature and precipitation stations. For the ‘warm and wet period’ extreme, each temperature station was linked to the nearest precipitation station, and the occurrence of this extreme was then calculated for all 34 station pairs. Further, for multi-day extremes, every day the extreme lasted longer than the definitions’ minimum was counted as an extra extreme event. For spring and summer drought and warm winter the EWE occurrence is recorded as a binary variable (i.e., 0 = not present; 1 = present) alongside an indicator of intensity. Moreover, the ‘warm winter’ and ‘wet field during plowing’ vulnerable periods start in December and October, respectively. Data from 2017 were required to calculate the frequency of these extremes in the year 2018. There were no data available for this period or part of this period for one temperature and one precipitation station; these values were replaced with precipitation and temperature data from the nearest station. Finally, as control variables, average temperature, maximum temperature, average and total precipitation, and number of rainy days during the growing period of potatoes and seed onions, as well as the number of frost days per year, are recorded. The growing season of seed potatoes is reported to be from March to September, for ware and starch potatoes from March to October, and for seed onions from February to October [19,54]. These start days of the growing season correspond to the earliest planting of survey respondents, however for some respondents the growing season starts much later, and ends a month later than the end of the growing season reported in the literature (Table 2).

2.3. Data analysis

Spatial data on postal code zones in the Netherlands [86] and the coordinates of weather stations [87,88] are used to match each postal zone to the closest precipitation and temperature station, calculated from the centroid of each postal zone. The hazard data and the survey data were then linked based on the postal codes provided by the survey respondents (similar to Refs. [21,89,90]). Survey data were matched to 14 temperature and 33 precipitation stations. Kruskal-Wallis one-way ANOVA (analysis of variance) rank tests were used to determine whether there were any significant differences in impact and physical vulnerability based on provinces, age, or farm size. To determine if there were any significant differences in hazard occurrence between the five study years, between provinces, or based on distance to the coast, *t* tests, ANOVA and Tukey Honest Significant Difference (Tukey HSD) tests were used. To determine the role of coastal distance on hazard and impact, each precipitation station was assigned to one of four regions: 0–25 km (km; *n* = 37), 25–50 km (*n* = 31), 50–100 km (*n* = 12), or 100–200 km (*n* = 1) from the coast (similar to Ref. [24]). It was found that heatwaves and warm winters occurred the most further inland, whereas extreme precipitation events occurred more along the coast during the study period. For a more detailed description of spatial and temporal differences in EWE occurrence, see Appendix C.

Panel regression models were created to determine which hazard and vulnerability indicators help to explain the variance in EWE impact. Six models were created for each of the three crops: i) hazard; ii) social vulnerability; iii) physical vulnerability; iv) combined vulnerability; v) combined hazard vulnerability model; and vi) selection with highest model fit. The dependent variable in all models is the impact on revenue per crop. The explanatory variables for the hazard model are the EWEs and control variables mentioned in Section 2.2. For social and physical vulnerability, the variables are listed in Appendix B. Farm gate prices for ware potato and seed onion were also included to test if this improved model fit in the social vulnerability models [91,92],³ which was not the case for any of the crops. Age and farm size were included in all social vulnerability and combined models of all crops, even if they reduced model fit, to compare their effects across the three crops and see the significance of these commonly included indicators. The same was done with crop diversity in the physical vulnerability model. Combined vulnerability and combined hazard vulnerability models were created based on the final variables included in the hazard, social, and physical vulnerability models.

The combination of variables that had the most explanatory power, as measured by the adjusted R-squared, were kept in the models. It was tested for all models whether the inclusion of factors for provinces, municipalities, years, and coastal distance increased model fit. This was the case for factors for provinces for 13 out of 15 regression models; none of the other factors improved model fit. Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) analysis was used to assess which variables have a high correlation with other variables and should be excluded to reduce multicollinearity. When the VIF value was over 5, the variable was excluded (based on [93]). A Hausman test [94] and F test were used to determine if a fixed effects (FE), random effects (RE), or pooled ordinary least squares (OLS) model performed better; one of the final models is a Pooled OLS model, the others are RE models. When serial autocorrelation or cross-sectional dependence (CD) was present according to a Breusch-Godfrey and Pesaran CD test respectively, heteroskedasticity-consistent robust standard errors (RSEs) were reported in the regression tables.⁴ All statistical tests were performed in the open-source statistical software R [96].

3. Results

3.1. Survey data analysis

3.1.1. Impact

Most farmers experienced a decline in revenue for seed potato, ware and starch potato, and seed onion at least once between 2018 and 2022 (87.0 %, 85.1 %, and 77.6 % of farmers, respectively). On average, farmers earned less than expected in two out of five years. In 2020, one farmer could not harvest at all due to extreme weather, which also happened to two seed onion farmers in 2021 and 2022 respectively. The average reported impact of EWEs on revenue was negative for all three crops from 2018 to 2021, while in 2022, the average reported effect was positive (but with large range). The severity of the impacts varied between crops, but the median impacts were the worst in 2018 for all three crops (Fig. 2); this was a year with a severe drought, i.e. high precipitation deficits [97] in the majority of the country (Appendix C). EWEs had a significantly more detrimental impact on seed onion cultivation in the southwestern part of the Netherlands, while in the north the impacts reported for seed onions were significantly more positive in 2020 and 2021.

3.1.2. Vulnerability

3.1.2.1. Social vulnerability. There is a lot of variation on the social vulnerability proxies (Appendix B). For instance, while most of the respondents rely on arable farming as their main source of income, dependence on agricultural income varies from 0 % to 100 % between respondents. Furthermore, the number of respondents with extensive weather insurance grew from 23.1 % in 2018 to 36.9 % in 2022. Exposure variables also vary strongly for farmers, with farm size ranging from 3.5 ha to 591 ha. For ware and starch potato, the acreage differs the most, ranging from 2 to 315 ha, compared to 1–86 and 1.5–45 ha for seed potato and seed onion, respectively. Farmers who had adopted an extensive weather insurance owned larger farms on average (90 % confidence level).

3.1.2.2. Physical vulnerability. There is also a lot of variation between respondents on most physical vulnerability indicators. Out of 32 included adaptation practices, fifteen have been implemented by more than half of respondents at least once between 2018 and 2022, with traditional drainage, cover crops, seed onion irrigation, seed potato irrigation, and chemical protection of onions being

³ No data were available on farm-gate prices for seed potato and starch potato.

⁴ Pesaran CD test was chosen over the Breusch-Pagan Lagrange multiplier test for cross-sectional dependence, as the former is preferable when the number of respondents exceeds the number of time periods in the dataset [95].

Table 2

Comparison of the planting and harvesting weeks for seed potato, ware and starch potato, and seed onion in the Netherlands provided in the literature [19,54,73] and by survey respondents.

Crop	Literature		Survey	
	Planting	Harvesting	Planting	Harvesting
Seed potato	9–18	26–40	9–30	27–44
Ware and starch potato	9–18	35–44	9–23	31–48
Seed onion	5–18	35–44	5–20	26–49

Fig. 2. Distribution of impacts from extreme weather events on seed potato, ware and starch potato, and seed onion farmers in the Netherlands from 2018 to 2022. The impact is measured as the deviation of obtained revenue from expected revenue.

implemented by more than 85 % of respondents.⁵ For the remaining practices, the adoption is moderate.

Most respondents experienced no difficulties with pesticide spraying as a result of EWEs. In 2021, EWEs affected pesticide spraying for ware and starch cultivation significantly more than in other years. In that year, prolonged wet periods during the ware and starch potato vulnerable period also occurred significantly more (Appendix C). A minority of respondents had no access to irrigation water during the study period. Access to irrigation water was significantly lower in the southwestern part of the country compared to the rest of the country, for all three crops. Respondents who lacked access to irrigation water, reported more detrimental effects of EWEs on seed onion revenue.

Farmers who adopted seed onion irrigation, seed onion pesticide spraying, mechanic cooling, pest resistant potato varieties, and traditional drainage owned larger farms, on average. Moreover, irrigation of seed potatoes was more commonly applied among farmers cultivating seed potatoes on more land. Water conserving soil tillage and cultivating heat resistant potato varieties were more commonly applied by farmers cultivating ware and starch potato on more land (the latter significant at 90 % confidence level), and land levelling was more commonly applied by farmers cultivating seed onions on more land. For the other 23 adaptation measures, there are no significant differences in adoption of adaptation measures and average farm size or cultivated land over 2018–2022. However, for three other measures there are significant effects between adoption of the measure and cultivated land for at least one year of the study period: the farms that had implemented wide ridges in 2018 had a larger farm size on average, whereas farms that had implemented intercropping in 2018 had a smaller farm size on average. Moreover, the use of lighter agricultural machinery was higher in 2019 and 2022 among smaller-scale seed onion farmers. Besides farm size, adoption also differs by age for three adaptation measures (90 % confidence level): farmers who implemented intercropping, pest-resistant potato varieties, and ware & starch potato

⁵ The 32 farm adaptation are included in Table B1, Appendix B. Note: in the survey, the farmers were asked about their difficulty spraying pesticide and irrigating cropland. The farmers who did not report difficulty are included here as farms where these adaptation practices were implemented.

pesticide spraying, were older on average.

3.1.3. Risk perception

Respondents perceived extreme rainfall and drought to have the greatest impact on crop cultivation at their farms, followed by extreme heat. The high risk perception of extreme heat and drought is congruent with the high occurrence of drought and extreme heat during the study period, with drought and heatwaves affecting the majority of the weather stations in the Netherlands on average during 2018–2022. Extreme rainfall occurrence was low during the study period, however, as the majority of locations with weather stations did not experience extreme rainfall (Appendix C).

3.2. Extreme weather impacts on crop revenue

3.2.1. Seed onion

The panel regression models in Table 3 explain variation in farm-level impacts of extreme weather events on seed onions. Model 6 includes five hazard variables, of which four are significant. A drought during summer is the only not significant variable in this model and the coefficient size varies across models, the occurrence of this extreme is associated with a 0.27–0.85 percentage point revenue loss. The control hazard variable ‘number of rainy days’ during the growing season is also associated with a revenue loss and the coefficient is significant and similar across models, with an extra day with rainfall linked to 0.87–0.89 percentage point revenue loss. Total precipitation and a warm and wet period are both significant in the model and have a slight positive effect on revenue: 100 mm extra rainfall is associated with 0.5–1.7 percentage point revenue increase, and a warm and wet period with a 1.7–2.0 percentage point increase. Extreme heat events have a consistently positive and significant coefficient across all models, and are associated with a 15.7–17.8 percentage points higher revenue.

Additionally, the final model (6) includes no social vulnerability proxies besides the control variables age and farm size. Both are not significant, and coefficient sizes vary across the models, particularly for age. A one year increase in age is associated with 0.37–1.07 percentage points more revenue, whereas an extra hectare of farm land is linked to 0.03–0.08 percentage points revenue loss. Four other proxies were included in the social vulnerability model (Model 2), but they were removed from both Model 4 and 6, as they reduced model fit.

Furthermore, model 6 includes five physical vulnerability variables besides the control variable crop diversity; all physical vulnerability variables are considered adaptation measures. Crop diversity is not significant in any of the models, and the coefficient size and sign are not consistent across models. Three out of five physical vulnerability indicators are linked to a reduction in revenue: taking pest prevention measures, incorporating measures to improve soil quality, and cultivating water-stress resistant crops. The former is not significant in model 5 but is in the other models, the latter two are significant in all models. Taking pest prevention measures is associated with a 10.8–20.1 percentage point loss in revenue, cultivating water-stress resistant crops with 40.6–55.7 percentage points lower revenue, and taking measures that improve soil quality with 20.0–23.7 percentage points lower revenue. In contrast, improving water availability at the farm-level and cultivating heat resistant crops are associated with higher revenues. Enhanced water availability was not significant in this model and was removed in model 4 as it removed model fit. The coefficient for cultivating heat resistant crops is significant and similar across models; this adaptation measure is associated with a 21.2–25.4 percentage points higher revenue.

Lastly, model 6 explains 38.0 % of the variance in EWE farm-level impacts on seed onions. By removing four social vulnerability variables and two physical vulnerability variables from model 5, model fit improved with 3.6 percentage points. Most of the variance is explained by physical vulnerability variables, followed by the hazard variables.

3.2.2. Seed potato

The panel regression models in Table 4 explain variation in farm-level impacts of extreme weather events on seed potato. Because the hazard, social, and physical vulnerability models combined include more variables than there are respondents, no combined regression models are included in Table 4. Hence, comparison of the coefficients across models is not possible. The physical vulnerability model explains approximately double the variance compared to the hazard and social vulnerability models.

For the hazard variables a warm winter and wet field during harvest are the only significant variables in the model. Both are linked to revenue loss, with a warm winter being associated with a 16.7 percentage point revenue loss, and a wet field during harvest with 0.88 percentage points. In the social vulnerability model the control variables (age and farm size) are not significant, but the other variables: total acreage of seed potato, number of employees, and number of farm owners, are significant. An extra hectare of land used for seed potato cultivation is associated with a 0.41 percentage point higher revenue and one extra full-time employee at the farm is linked to 7.29 percentage points higher revenue. An extra owner for the farm is linked to 13.64 percentage points lower revenue, however. Lastly, the inclusion of five adaptation measures besides crop diversity led to the best model fit for the physical vulnerability model. All variables are significant. Cultivating a larger variety of crops, planting drought resistant and heat resistant crops, and difficulty spraying are all associated with a reduction in revenue due to EWEs, whereas planting in wider ridges and enhanced water availability are linked to higher revenue.

3.2.3. Ware and starch potato

The panel regression models in Table 5 explain variation in farm-level impacts of extreme weather events on ware and starch potato. The model with the highest model fit (model 6) includes six hazard variables, all of which are significant. The hazard variables

Table 3
Panel regression results for the models with seed onion impact as the dependent variable.

Variable	1) Hazard	2) Social vulnerability	3) Physical vulnerability	4) Combined vulnerability	5) Complete	6) Selection
Drought summer (I)	−0.848** (0.273)				−0.278 (0.395)	−0.491 (0.370)
Extreme heat	15.704* (7.386)				17.817 (9.513)	16.996 (9.277)
Rainy days	−0.889*** (0.269)				−0.874* (0.368)	−0.883* (0.348)
Total precipitation	0.005 (0.005)				0.017* (0.007)	0.014* (0.007)
Warm and wet	1.661* (0.777)				2.001* (0.963)	1.816 (0.929)
Age		1.067* (0.541)		0.506 (0.353)	0.864 (0.510)	0.372 (0.370)
Educational attainment		10.032 (7.518)			3.088 (6.478)	
Farm size		−0.039 (0.061)		−0.031 (0.048)	−0.076 (0.053)	−0.056 (0.048)
Household size		8.302* (4.148)			5.684 (3.978)	
Knowledge vocational educ.		10.456 (9.483)			−1.192 (8.305)	
Ownership		−6.470 (5.776)			−4.123 (5.701)	
Crop diversity			2.962 (2.343)	−0.460 (2.645)	1.530 (3.323)	1.336 (2.609)
Drought resistant crops			12.095 (7.070)		2.971 (12.382)	
Heat resistant crops			28.354*** (6.595)	35.861*** (10.092)	26.533* (12.690)	33.976*** (9.842)
<i>Soil quality improvement</i>			−23.076*** (4.657)	−23.749*** (6.642)	−19.980* (9.011)	−21.650*** (6.514)
<i>Water availability</i>			6.710* (3.128)		3.928 (5.572)	3.358 (4.302)
<i>Pest prevention</i>			−16.031** (5.440)	−17.007* (8.477)	−10.759 (11.142)	−20.134* (8.346)
Water-stress resistant crops			−51.986*** (8.518)	−55.229*** (10.621)	−47.547** (15.524)	−52.875*** (10.646)
Wide ridges			−17.127* (7.455)		−2.958 (13.942)	
Constant	75.440* (32.694)	−52.556 (44.078)	20.184* (8.926)	28.188 (26.640)	−21.440 (60.287)	29.537 (48.034)
Province fixed effects	X	X	X	X	X	X
Adj. R-squared	0.175	0.132	0.325	0.341	0.344	0.380
Observations	200	131	155	136	131	136
Model	RE	RE	Pooled OLS	RE	RE	RE

Note: Significance levels: · = 0.10; * = 0.05; ** = 0.01; *** = 0.001. The standard error is reported in between brackets; for the physical vulnerability model these are robust standard errors. Number of employees and dependency ratio are excluded from model 2, due to the non-response rate. Irrigation is removed from model 3, due to the non-response rate. (I) refers to intensity of the hazard (as opposed to a binary variable for the presence of the hazard). The bold variables are variables that are included in all crop models. The variables in italics are composite variables; water availability is quantitatively measured, the other two are binary variables.

number of frost days and maximum temperature are not significant in any of the other models, and are the only variables associated with an increase in revenue (Table 5). The four other hazard variables are significant in all models and have similar coefficient sizes. A drought during summer is associated with 9.7–11.3⁶ percentage points revenue loss, and every additional day of drought with 0.59–0.92 percentage point extra revenue loss. The effect of the other EWEs is smaller, with an extra rainy day per year linked to 0.64–0.79 percentage points of revenue loss, and a wet period during plowing with 0.45–0.65 percentage points revenue loss.

Additionally, model 6 includes four social vulnerability variables besides the control variables age and farm size. Age and educational attainment are associated with a revenue gain, the other proxies with a revenue loss. The coefficient for age is not significant and similar across the models. For educational attainment, the coefficient size is similar across models 2, 4 and 6, but is lower in model 5 (the complete model). Based on models 2, 4, and 6 a theoretical educational attainment (see footnote 2 Section 2.1.2 for the details on educational attainment scales) is associated with 23.4–23.9 percentage points higher revenue compared to moderate theoretical education, and 46.8–47.8 percentage points compared to practical education. However, when the obtained university or university of applied sciences degree was on a topic related to agriculture, these effects are 13.5–20.1 percentage points lower. Gaining agricultural knowledge through family is dropped in both combined models as it reduced model fit. The coefficients for farm size and agricultural dependence are similar across models and both variables are associated with a small loss of revenue. The latter is

⁶ Coefficients for drought summer intensity (I) and drought summer presence (P) combined.

Table 4
Panel regression results for the models with ware and starch potato impact as the dependent variable.

Variable	1) Hazard	2) Social vulnerability	3) Physical vulnerability
Drought spring (I)	−0.353 (0.328)		
Extreme rainfall	2.373 (2.040)		
Extreme heat	15.142 (10.330)		
Rainy days	−0.141 (0.214)		
Warm winter (P)	−16.749* (7.903)		
Wet field harvest	−0.883 (0.465)		
Wet field plowing	0.291 (0.204)		
Acreage		0.410* (0.172)	
Age		−0.398 (0.370)	
Employees		7.294* (3.409)	
Farm size		−0.093 (0.060)	
Ownership		−13.638** (4.232)	
Crop diversity			−8.598*** (0.548)
Drought resistant crops			−9.925 (5.585)
Heat resistant crops			−11.699* (5.447)
Spraying difficulty			−28.455 (16.564)
<i>Water availability B</i>			13.644*** (3.902)
Wide ridges			18.518*** (3.936)
Constant			40.484*** (4.198)
Province fixed effects	X		
Adj. R-squared	0.199	0.190	0.384
Observations	113	70	70
Model	RE	RE	RE

Note: Significance levels: · = 0.10; * = 0.05; ** = 0.01; *** = 0.001. Standard errors are reported in between brackets; for the physical vulnerability model these are robust standard errors. (I) refers to intensity of the hazard, (P) to presence of the hazard (binary variable). The bold variables are variables that are included in all crop models. The variable in italics is a composite variable (binary). Spring drought presence is not included in the model due to a high correlation (>0.8) with drought spring intensity.

significant in all, while the former is significant in all but model 5. Every 1 % increase in dependence on arable farming for income is associated with a 0.25–0.33 percentage point loss of revenue, while an extra hectare of farm land is linked to 0.07–0.09 percentage points revenue loss.

Furthermore, model 6 includes the control variable crop diversity and three other physical vulnerability indicators. The coefficient for crop diversity varies across models and is not significant in any of them. Only planting in wide ridges is significant in all models (Model 3–6), and this adaptation measure is associated with 22.1–32.9 percentage points revenue loss from EWEs. The other two adaptation measures, i.e. taking sprout prevention measures and cultivating water-stress resistant crops are associated with an increase in revenue. The coefficient sizes are similar across models for both measures. Sprout prevention is linked to 10.6–15.1 percentage point higher revenue, while cultivating water-stress resistant crops is linked to 13.1–19.4 percentage points higher revenue. The latter was not significant in the final model, but was significant in the other models. Soil type and difficulty spraying are both dropped from this final model and from the combined vulnerability model.

Lastly, the final model explains 22.0 % of the variance in reported EWE impacts on ware and starch potatoes. The removal of two physical vulnerability and one social vulnerability variable from the complete model improved model fit with 3.3 percentage points. When controlling for sample size, the hazard variables account for approximately half of the explained variance, the rest is explained by the vulnerability variables, social vulnerability in particular.

Table 5
Panel regression results for the models with ware and starch potato impact as the dependent variable.

Variable	1) Hazard	2) Social vulnerability	3) Physical vulnerability	4) Combined vulnerability	5) Complete	6) Selection
Drought summer (I)	-0.588** (0.216)				-0.710** (0.274)	-0.923*** (0.272)
Drought summer (P)	-10.229* (4.0445)				-10.612* (5.194)	-8.744 (5.268)
Frost days	1.709 (1.400)				1.259 (1.846)	3.156 (1.712)
Maximum temperature	2.031 (1.145)				1.345 (1.400)	2.641 (1.392)
Rainy days	-0.665*** (0.179)				-0.635** (0.229)	-0.794*** (0.226)
Wet field plowing	-0.446 (0.262)				-0.548 (0.329)	-0.648* (0.317)
Age		0.465 (0.269)		0.326 (0.283)	0.038 (0.413)	0.135 (0.341)
Agricultural dependence		-0.249** (0.092)		-0.288** (0.087)	-0.253 (0.147)	-0.329** (0.123)
Dependency ratio		-4.953 (3.127)		-4.886 (3.023)	-7.403 (4.976)	-4.670 (3.862)
Educational attainment		23.903*** (3.739)		23.723*** (5.473)	18.094* (8.594)	23.416*** (6.853)
Knowledge family		-8.039 (5.224)			-7.823 (8.730)	
Knowledge higher education		-13.540* (6.216)		-20.073** (6.889)	-15.643 (11.646)	-19.260* (9.228)
Farm size		-0.067 (0.040)		-0.093 (0.050)	-0.078 (0.059)	-0.093 (0.055)
Crop diversity			1.292 (2.648)	0.494 (2.553)	3.371 (3.567)	1.597 (2.723)
Clay soil ^a			-13.030 (9.660)		-9.843 (14.956)	
Spraying difficulty			-10.939 (7.472)		-13.110* (6.503)	
<i>Sprout prevention</i>			12.303 (6.542)	15.116** (5.163)	10.598 (7.889)	14.335* (7.038)
Water-stress resistant crops			19.404 (11.422)	16.817 (8.549)	19.083 (11.181)	13.131 (9.353)
Wide ridges			-22.092* (10.975)	-22.490 (12.049)	-32.895* (15.676)	-27.267* (13.281)
Constant		-40.151 (18.510)	-9.405 (15.278)	-38.539 (20.851)	-1.846 (56.574)	-45.670 (52.044)
Province factor	X	X	X	X	X	X
Adj. R-squared	0.106	0.127	0.067	0.154	0.187	0.220
Observations	324	220	235	215	205	215
Model	RE	RE	RE	RE	RE	RE

Note: Significance levels: · = 0.10; * = 0.05; ** = 0.01; *** = 0.001. Standard errors are reported in between brackets. (I) refers to intensity of the hazard, (P) to presence of the hazard (binary variable). SE refers to standard error, RSE to robust standard error. The bold variables are variables that are included in all crop models. The variable in italics is a composite variable (binary variable). ^a This is a dummy variable for soil type; sandy soil is the default option.

4. Discussion

The results described in the previous section show that most of the surveyed farmers in this study incurred financial losses because of EWEs between 2018 and 2022. The impact reported by survey respondents ranges from a complete loss of revenue to a revenue doubling. According to the findings, this variation is caused in part by geographic differences in hazard occurrence, as well as differences in the physical and social vulnerability of the farmers. For all three crops drought and high temperatures explained part of the variance. Other hazard variables that explained the variance for two or more of the crops were wet fields during plowing and the control variable number of rainy days. There were no similarities in the social vulnerability variables included for the three crops besides the control variables age and farm size; agricultural dependence, educational attainment, and farm ownership were the main social vulnerability indicators that helped explain inter-farm variance. For physical vulnerability, cultivating resistant crops for either drought, water-stress or heat, were common indicators for the three crops. The other important adaptation practices were planting in wide ridges and enhanced water availability.

According to Diogo et al. [29], the northeastern part of the Netherlands (Drenthe and the south of Groningen) is the most vulnerable to the effects of CC and EWEs. Because only 6 % of respondents are from Drenthe, it could not be determined whether the effects of EWEs were already more negative there. However, the reported impacts for seed onion cultivation were significantly more negative in Zeeland (southwest of the country). This is most likely because seed onions are more susceptible to drought than potatoes [18,19], and Zeeland is more susceptible during droughts since farmers report lower access to irrigation water there, as is consistent

with the findings by van Oort et al. [23].

4.1. Weather extremes

Panel regression analyses revealed drought as a significant factor in explaining the variability of EWE impacts on seed onion, ware and starch potatoes (drought during summer), and seed potato cultivation (drought during spring). Droughts were also identified by Reidsma et al. [18], as one of the EWEs that cause the most damage to seed onions. However, previous literature did not consider drought as a significant factor affecting potato cultivation in the Netherlands [18,19,54], and projected the impact of drought on the economic output of the Dutch agricultural sector as a whole to be low now and in the future [29,54]. These conclusions seem to contradict the findings here and the perceived high risks of droughts on potatoes and onions among surveyed farmers in this study and among a previous study in Zeeland [21]. A potential explanation is that Schaap et al. [19,54], Reidsma et al. [18], and Diogo et al. [29], used definitions of extreme events by arable farmers from the north of the Netherlands, where drought is a smaller problem due to irrigation access. Moreover, as these studies are from 2009, 2013, 2015 and 2017 respectively, i.e. before the severe summer drought of 2018, risk perceptions among potato farmers might have been lower during that time. However, it is also possible that the impact of drought on the overall farming sector is indeed minor, but is a bigger source of local revenue losses. This would imply that drought can exacerbate inequality between farms, particularly because irrigation access varies by province and is lower among smaller-scale farmers (Section 3.1.2). Irrigation was, however, not identified as a physical vulnerability variable that explained variance between respondents. This could be because many of the respondents were from Zeeland, and because the response rate on this variable was low, so it was excluded from the analysis for the seed onion regression.

Other EWEs identified in the panel regressions that explain inter-farm variation in impacts on potatoes are wet fields during harvest and plowing, warm winters, extreme heat events, and extreme rainfall events. These results are largely consistent with the literature. According to Reidsma et al. [18], the three most detrimental weather extremes for potato cultivation in the current climate are warm winters, heatwaves, and extreme rainfall, and van Oort et al. [22] also identified wet field during harvest as an important explanatory variable for potato yield anomalies. While warm winters was only included in the regression model for seed potatoes, in the ware and starch potato models the control variable frost days was linked to higher revenues, indicating that warmer winters affect potatoes negatively. This is also consistent with the high risk perception of Zeelandic farmers for reduced frost days [21]. Moreover, while heatwaves were not part of any of the regression models, extreme heat was part of the seed potato regression model, as was extreme rainfall, and maximum temperature was part of the ware and starch potato model.

For onions, the EWEs that were identified in the panel regression besides summer drought were warm and wet periods and extreme heat. Both warm and wet periods and extreme heat were linked to more positive revenue. Extreme heat has not been identified in other studies as an extreme affecting onions [18,19,73]. However, warm and wet periods are identified by Reidsma et al. [18] as the most detrimental to seed onions besides drought, which contrasts the findings here, where we see a positive effect.

A limitation of the extreme weather assessment is that EWE frequency and intensity were quantified based on the susceptible periods during the average growing season of potatoes and onions (Table 1). Since the growing season for some respondents differed strongly from the average growing season, the counted EWEs might not be an accurate representation of the actual occurrence of extremes during the susceptible period of the crops. Due to the high non-response rate on the planting and harvesting date questions, it was not possible to calculate the frequency and intensity of extremes based on individual respondent's growing seasons in this research. Future studies should consider using a wider planting and harvesting range when determining the vulnerable period toward EWEs. Including week numbers of EWE occurrence could further improve the accuracy, since the timing of extreme events can affect the magnitude of impacts [20].

4.2. Vulnerability

The panel regressions showed that vulnerability is a key factor in understanding farm-level impacts of EWEs on potato and seed onion crops. For seed onions, physical vulnerability was the main factor contributing to inter-farm differences in impacts, followed by the hazard variables, with social vulnerability being the least important component. For ware and starch potato, social vulnerability and hazard were approximately equally important. For seed potato, physical vulnerability was the most important component, followed by social vulnerability and hazard. These findings underscore the importance of considering social vulnerability when studying the effects of extreme weather events on agriculture, an aspect that previous studies on the Dutch arable farming sector have overlooked (e.g. Refs. [18,19,22,29]).

4.2.1. Social vulnerability

While social vulnerability was not very important for explaining the variance for seed onion, social vulnerability proxies like age and farm size influenced physical vulnerability as well, as the implementation of several climate adaptation measures was lower among younger and smaller-scale farmers. That social vulnerability factors like age and farm size affect adoption of climate adaptation measures has been reported before in other studies [98–100]. Larger and more profitable farms are typically more likely to adopt adaptation measures (e.g. Refs. [101–103]), which contributes to larger inter-farm inequalities, in regards to susceptibility to EWEs.

Besides affecting adoption rates, larger farm-size was also associated with more detrimental impacts from EWEs for ware and starch potato; for the other crops the coefficient was also negative, but this relationship was not significant. This negative relationship contradicts the assumptions in other studies that smaller-scale farmers are more vulnerable to extremes [46,55]. A potential explanation is a reporting bias in impacts. The acreage of cultivated ware and starch potato varied strongly between respondents; more than for the other two crops. Eggers et al. [104] detected that smaller-scale farmers in Germany were less aware of climate change impacts than larger-scale farmers; so the reported impacts by smaller-scale farmers in this sample could potentially be underestimated.

Besides age and farm size, the social vulnerability proxies educational attainment, agricultural dependence, and gaining agricultural knowledge through university or university of applied sciences were all significant in explaining the variation in impacts for ware and starch potatoes. A higher dependence on agriculture as an income source, was associated with more detrimental impacts of EWEs, which is consistent with a study in Kenya that found that income diversity increases the resilience of farmers to EWEs [105]. A more theoretical educational attainment was linked to more positive impacts on revenue, although this effect was lower when the degree was obtained on a topic related to agriculture. The findings on educational attainment are in line with the results reported in previous studies that more years of education is linked to implementation of more farm adaptation measures [98,99]; however, this does not explain why the effect is lower when the degree is on a topic related to farming.

One main limitation of this research is that impact of EWEs is based on self-reported data, which may not be entirely accurate. Respondents were asked to indicate how much their revenue differed from their expected revenue due to EWEs, but some respondents may have reported the overall revenue deviation instead of just the loss or gain attributed to EWEs. Previous literature has reported that attribution of EWEs to climate change can differ between the general population and scientists, and can depend on media exposure and demographic characteristics [106,107]. While respondents were not asked to attribute EWEs to CC in this study, the attribution of crop impacts to EWE occurrence by farmers, could similarly have differed among demographic groups and media exposure, and from scientific attributions. Another limitation is that the questions regarding ware and starch potato were asked together in the survey, even though some farmers cultivate both crops and impacts could have differed between the crops. This could have forced respondents to provide an average answer. In future studies, it would be beneficial to separate these two crops in the questions. This could also be why the model fit for the ware and starch potato model is lower compared to the seed potato and seed onion models.

4.2.2. Physical vulnerability

Through the panel regressions we do not find strong support for the assumption in the literature that higher crop diversity increases the resilience of farmers [67,69]. While this physical vulnerability proxy was linked to higher revenue for seed onion and ware and starch potato, this was not significant. For seed potato, higher crop diversity was significantly associated with revenue losses from EWEs. Besides this control variable, the panel regression models identified ten other physical vulnerability indicators that explain the variance in EWE impacts between respondents, seven of which were also included in the best model-fit model. Cultivating heat resistant crops, cultivating water-stress resistant ware & starch potato crops, taking sprout prevention measures, and increasing the farm-level availability of water were linked to less detrimental impacts of EWEs, as hypothesized based on the literature [73]. Cultivating water-stress resistant seed onion crops, improving soil quality, taking pest prevention measures, and planting ware and starch potatoes in wider ridges were linked to more detrimental impacts, despite the hypothesis in the literature that these practices reduce the physical vulnerability of farmers [73,76]. However, the negative coefficient does not necessarily mean the measures are ineffective. First, improved soil quality refers to the application of lighter machinery and intercropping, both of which were implemented more by smaller-scale (seed onion) farmers in part of the study period, which could explain the negative sign. Second, a small group of respondents implemented pest prevention and planted in wider ridges, which could explain the coefficient. Furthermore, Reidsma et al. [18] report that planting in wider ridges only becomes effective in reducing negative effects from extremes in a warmer climate. Planting in wider ridges can reduce heat stress for crops, but fewer potato crops can be cultivated per hectare with this practice. The subsequent reduction in yield will only be outweighed in warmer climates with more heatwaves [18]. Lastly, there were only five respondents who cultivated water-stress resistant seed onion crops, of which three were from Zeeland, where drought susceptibility is higher (section 4.1), which could (partly) explain the large negative coefficient on this variable in the seed onion regression model.

4.2.3. Limitations vulnerability assessment

In addition to the limitations discussed earlier, there are other limitations to the measurement of vulnerability and impact in this study. To begin with, the assumption made in this study that the most vulnerable farmers are those with the highest financial losses from EWEs is criticized by Cutter & Finch [108] because impacts might not be highest in the most vulnerable communities. While impacts were quantified in relative terms instead of absolute terms, to avoid the underappreciation of impacts of smaller-scale farmers, the focus on monetary impacts and impacts at the farm-owner level disregarded other effects of EWEs such as farmer health [13] and potential layoffs of seasonal workers [14]. This assessment is, therefore, only suitable for determining which factors contribute to a higher vulnerability to financial losses from EWEs at the farm-owner level, and not for other forms of agricultural vulnerability. Furthermore, vulnerability is not static and can change over time. This was not accounted for in this study, as that is not possible with an analysis of past hazard impacts [109]. This limits the ability to draw meaningful conclusions about the most vulnerable regions to EWEs in the Netherlands in the future, as the effect of vulnerability indicators could differ temporally (such as planting in wide ridges as mentioned above).

Lastly, the panel regression results may have been affected by omitted variable bias. Factors for the Dutch provinces were included in thirteen out of fifteen panel regression models, because it improved model fit. This means the included hazard and vulnerability variables were insufficient for accounting for all geographical differences in impacts. To gain a better understanding of the differences in EWE impacts, it is necessary to conduct additional research into the factors that explain this geographical variation. Future research could include factors such as groundwater salinity, elevation, and evaporation as these may affect hazard occurrence and crop vulnerability levels [24,54,56,110].

4.3. Policy implications

It would be helpful for policymakers to know that the majority of surveyed farmers in the Netherlands have experienced a decline in

revenue at least once between 2018 and 2022, as this may create a sense of urgency to improve and implement local and national level adaptation policies. Further, policies must reflect the importance of social vulnerability on the impacts of EWEs on farms, instead of merely focusing on reducing crop vulnerability, for instance, by expanding focus to income diversification for farmers. Moreover, it is helpful for policymakers to know which adaptation practices to promote to mitigate the effects of CC and EWEs, in particular in low-lying and densely populated countries like the Netherlands, where common farm adaptation strategies such as migration [111,112] and cultivation at higher altitudes [113,114] are not feasible.

Policies promoting farm-level adaptation should recognize that smaller and younger farmers appear to have unequal access to adaptation strategies, despite policies in place to address this. The 'Rural Development Program' (2014–2022), that was part of the EU's Common Agricultural Policy, allocated financial resources to support younger farmers in accessing sustainable technologies [115]. The 'National Strategic Plan' (2023–2027) succeeding this policy, aims to redistribute funds to smaller farms for a sustainable transition [116]. Monitoring the effectiveness of such policies in reducing inequality in climate change vulnerability between farms is crucial. Further, while these general agricultural policies include measures to reduce inequality in the Dutch agricultural sector, equal access to adaptation strategies has not been mentioned in the national 'Action Program Climate Adaptation Agriculture' of the Netherlands [117]. Policies should be streamlined and include equality at all levels to prevent the exacerbation of inter-farm inequalities and avoid maladaptive outcomes [118,119].

As dry summers and water availability were two important factors explaining inter-farm differences in extreme weather impact, policymakers should not overlook the impact of drought on agriculture, even if it may not have a significant impact on national revenue, as it could increase inequalities between farms. As freshwater becomes scarcer in the future, due to sea-level rise and subsequent salinization as well as more frequent dry periods [120], future water access may be more limited. It is important for policies to support alternative drought-coping measures for farmers, such as drought-resistant crops and increased water availability at the farm-level. While the national report 'Action Program Climate Adaptation Agriculture' already incorporates drought adaptation measures [117], the 'Climate Adaptation Strategy' of Zeeland does not mention water storage, irrigation access, and resistant crops to reduce physical vulnerability [110], despite the province's high vulnerability to drought.

Furthermore, policymakers could explore ways to support farmers that want to start cultivating less sensitive crops. While farmers with profit-maximizing objectives prefer to continue cultivating these valuable crops instead of switching to less sensitive crops [121], there have already been Dutch farmers that stopped cultivating potatoes and onions [21], and since the effects of EWEs are projected to grow, more farmers might want to switch to other crops in the future. Overall, it is worthwhile to further explore the needs of farmers regarding policies that aim to mitigate the vulnerability of arable farmers to EWEs.

5. Conclusion

This study examined the effects of extreme weather events on Dutch potato and seed onion farmers. The research considered differences in where these events occurred, the farm practices used, and the social vulnerability of respondents. The findings showed that extreme weather events already have a strong impact on farm revenues in the Netherlands. On average, there was a negative impact between 2018 and 2021, but a positive impact in 2022. The most severe impacts were seen in 2018, which coincided with a severe summer drought. Seed onions were more affected than potatoes during the study period, indicating that they are more susceptible to extreme weather events in the current climate. The reported impacts varied greatly among farmers, with some experiencing a complete reduction in revenue while others saw a doubling of their farm revenue.

This variation is partly explained by spatial differences in the intensity and frequency of extreme weather occurrence across the country. The extremes explaining most of the variation in impacts are droughts, warm winters, wet fields during harvest, wet fields during plowing, extreme rainfall, and extreme heat. A drought during summer was found to have a stronger effect on revenue than stated in previous, national-level assessments, implying that this extreme may not have a major impact on national losses, but is an important factor for revenue losses at the farm level. The impact of extreme weather events on seed onion revenues was significantly higher in Zeeland compared to the rest of the Netherlands. This is likely because Zeeland is more susceptible to drought, due to the low access to irrigation water there. This study also found that several adaptation practices were implemented more by larger-scale and older farmers, contributing to inequalities in the farm-level effects of extreme weather events.

This study was the first to quantify the impacts of past extreme weather events on revenue in the Dutch arable farming sector and assess the sources of inter-farm differences of these impacts. Vulnerability, both physical and social, was a key factor in explaining the observed differences in farm-level impacts, roughly equal in size to the effect of hazard variables. It was found that social vulnerability factors such as income diversity and more years of education help reduce the impact of extreme events at the farm level. These factors have often been overlooked in risk assessments and policies for the Dutch agricultural sector. The study's findings suggest that social vulnerability should be included in risk assessments and policy and that access barriers to adaptation practices should be further assessed and eliminated. The results also highlight the importance of examining the effects of extreme weather on a sub-national, farm-level scale to avoid overlooking factors that have little influence at a national level, such as dry summers. The inclusion of these factors in research and policy is crucial to prevent maladaptive outcomes and inter-farm inequalities from worsening when extreme weather events occur.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Anoek J. van Tilburg: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Thijs Endendijk:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Hans de Moel:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Anoek van Tilburg reports financial support was provided by European Commission. Thijs Endendijk reports financial support was provided by European Commission. Hans de Moel reports financial support was provided by European Commission. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendices.

Appendix A. Study area

Fig. A1. Location of temperature (left) and precipitation (right) stations of the KNMI in the Netherlands with daily data from 2018 to 2022. Map on the left includes the names of the Dutch provinces. The map is made in QGIS [60]. Data sources: [61,82,83,87,88].

Table A1

Comparison of the distribution of farm sizes per class and full-time employment equivalent (FTE) in the Netherlands and the survey.

Farm size class	Netherlands (2014–2016) ¹			Survey (2018–2022) ²		
	Acreage (ha)	Share (%)	FTE	Acreage (ha)	Share (%)	FTE
<50 ha	32	54	1.0	27	31	1.8
50–100 ha	70	32	1.5	68	35	1.8
100–150 ha	120	9	2.2	126	22	2.1
150–200 ha	172	4	2.7	169	7	2.8
≥200 ha	318	2	4.5	365	4	6.7
All farms	63	100	1.4	87	100	2.14

¹Data source: [122]; ²Based on the average of the five years.

Appendix B. Vulnerability survey questions

Table B1

Summary table vulnerability questions survey.

Variable name ¹	Variable definition	Asked annually	Obs.	Central tendency ³	Min	Max
Social vulnerability						
Acreage seed onion	Total number of hectares used for seed onion cultivation	Y	189	8.2	1.5	45
Acreage seed potato	Total number of hectares used for seed potato cultivation	Y	107	28.0	1	86
Acreage W&S potato	Total number of hectares used for ware and starch potato cultivation	Y	311	27.1	2	315
Age	Years of age on January 1st, 2023	N	58	52	30	74
Chronic illness	Number of people in the household of the farm owner that have a chronic illness or disability	N	57	0.1	0	2
Dependency ratio	Number of people in the farm owner's household over the age of 67 or under the age of 15	N	55	0.6	0	3
Education	Highest educational attainment based on three categories from 1 = Practical to 3 = Theoretical	N	58	((2))	1	3
Employees	Number of employees in the company (measured in full-time equivalent)	N	79	2.1	0.35	15
Farm size	Total number of hectares used for crop cultivation	Y	386	88.0	3.5	591
Household size	Number of people in the household of the farm owner	N	57	3.4	1	6
Income diversity	Share of economic result (%) that is earned with arable farming	N	58	77.9	0	100
Insurance	Take out an extensive weather insurance. 0 = No; 1 = Yes.	Y	322	29.5	0	1
Knowledge family	Gained knowledge about arable farming from family or friends: 0 = No; 1 = Yes	N	58	29.3	0	1
Knowledge vocational educ.	Gained knowledge about arable farming through vocational education: 0 = No; 1 = Yes	N	58	39.7	0	1
Knowledge university	Gained knowledge about arable farming from a university or university of applied sciences degree: 0 = No; 1 = Yes	N	58	34.5	0	1
Ownership	Number of owners the farm has.	N	61	1.7	1	4
Physical vulnerability ⁴						
General farm practices & characteristics						
Crop diversity	Average number of crops cultivated per year	N	77	5	2	10
Harvesting date seed onion	Week number of the last week of planting	Y	118	37	26	49
Harvesting date seed potato	Week number of the last week of planting	Y	60	37	27	44
Harvesting date W&S potato	Week number of the last week of planting	Y	204	41	31	48
Planting date seed potato	Week number of the first week of planting	Y	60	15	9	30
Planting date W&S potato	Week number of the first week of planting	Y	207	15	9	23
Soil type	Soil type most crops are cultivated on at the farm; 1 = sand; 2 = clay; 3 = loess; 4 = peat.	N	80	((2))	1	2
Sowing date seed onion	Week number of the first week of sowing	Y	122	13	5	20
Adaptation practices						
Chemical protection onions	Applying chemicals to protection onions against fungi. 0 = No; 1 = Yes.	Y	39	89.7	0	1
Cover crops	Plant crops to keep soil covered. 0 = No; 1 = Yes.	Y	65	98.5	0	1
Drip irrigation	Irrigation through pipes and tubes on the ground next to crops.	Y	65	1.5	0	1
Drought-resistant onion variety	Plant drought-resistant onion varieties. 0 = No; 1 = Yes.	Y	321	28.2	0	1
Drought-resistant potato variety	Plant drought-resistant potato varieties. 0 = No; 1 = Yes.	Y	311	36.5	0	1
Heat-resistant onion variety	Plant heat-resistant onion varieties. 0 = No; 1 = Yes.	Y	321	20.5	0	1
Heat-resistant potato variety	Plant heat-resistant potato varieties. 0 = No; 1 = Yes.	Y	311	22.2	0	1
High-density sowing onions	Sow a large amount of onions/hectare. 0 = No; 1 = Yes.	Y	321	25.6	0	1
Increase water storage	Increase storage capacity at the farm level (including weirs and ditches). 0 = No; 1 = Yes.	Y	65	32.3	0	1
Intercropping	Cultivate multiple crops at the same time at the same plot of land. 0 = No; 1 = Yes.	Y	65	10.8	0	1
Irrigation difficulty seed onion	No access to irrigation water. 0 = No (i.e., access to irrigation); 1 = Yes (i.e., no irrigation access)	Y	208	10.3	0	1
Irrigation difficulty seed potato	No access to irrigation water. 0 = No (i.e., access to irrigation); 1 = Yes (i.e., no irrigation access)	Y	107	13.3	0	1
Irrigation difficulty W&S potato	No access to irrigation water. 0 = No (i.e., access to irrigation); 1 = Yes (i.e., no irrigation access)	Y	296	23.7	0	1
Land levelling	Ensure surface of agricultural land is flat. 0 = No; 1 = Yes.	Y	65	69.2	0	1
Level-controlled drainage	Vary the level in drainage basins to control draining intensity. 0 = No; 1 = Yes.	Y	65	7.7	0	1
Light machinery	Use of light agricultural machinery on agricultural land. 0 = No; 1 = Yes.	Y	65	58.5	0	1

(continued on next page)

Table B1 (continued)

Variable name ¹	Variable definition	Asked annually	Obs.	Central tendency ³	Min	Max
Mechanic cooling potatoes	Cooling potatoes mechanically during storage. 0 = No; 1 = Yes.	Y	63	34.9	0	1
Pest-resistant onion variety	Plant pest-resistant onion varieties. 0 = No; 1 = Yes.	Y	321	28.2	0	1
Pest-resistant potato variety	Plant pest-resistant potato varieties. 0 = No; 1 = Yes.	Y	311	44.4	0	1
Spraying difficulty seed onion	Difficulty spraying due to extreme weather. 0 = No; 1 = Yes.	Y	208	22.9	0	1
Spraying difficulty seed potato	Difficulty spraying due to extreme weather. 0 = No; 1 = Yes.	Y	94	18.8	0	1
Spraying difficulty W&S potato	Difficulty spraying due to extreme weather. 0 = No; 1 = Yes.	Y	296	34.0	0	1
Sprout inhibitor application seed onion	Application of sprout inhibitor to seed onion to prevent sprouting during storage. 0 = No; 1 = Yes.	Y	195	80.0	0	1
Sprout inhibitor application seed potato	Application of sprout inhibitor to seed potato to prevent sprouting during storage. 0 = No; 1 = Yes.	Y	85	5.9	0	1
Sprout inhibitor application W&S potato	Application of sprout inhibitor to ware and starch potato to prevent sprouting during storage. 0 = No; 1 = Yes.	Y	275	76.4	0	1
Surface water drainage	Improved drainage of water from the surface of agricultural land. 0 = No; 1 = Yes.	Y	65	63.1	0	1
Traditional drainage	Drainage pipes in the agricultural soil. 0 = No; 1 = Yes.	Y	65	92.3	0	1
UV-light protection onions	Protection of onions with UV-light against fungi. 0 = No; 1 = Yes.	Y	39	5.1	0	1
Water conserving soil tillage	Superficial plowing and non-inversion tillage to minimize soil moisture losses. 0 = No. 1 = Yes.	Y	65	56.9	0	1
Water-stress-resistant onion variety	Plant water-stress-resistant onion varieties. 0 = No; 1 = Yes.	Y	321	12.8	0	1
Water-stress-resistant potato variety	Plant water-stress-resistant potato varieties. 0 = No; 1 = Yes.	Y	311	17.5	0	1
Wider ridges	Plant crops further apart. 0 = No; 1 = Yes.	Y	322	13.8	0	1

¹W&S stands for ware and starch; ² Mean, (Median), ((Mode)), *Percentage of respondents that answered yes.*

Table B2

Classification of physical vulnerability indicators.

Category	Included	Comment ^a
Drainage improvement	Land leveling Level-controlled drainage Surface water drainage	Traditional drainage excluded
Extreme rainfall adaptation	Land leveling Level-controlled drainage Surface water drainage	Traditional drainage excluded. Separate for onions and potatoes.
Heat adaptation ^b	Water-stress resistant crops Drip irrigation Heat resistant crops	Separate for onions and potatoes
Pest prevention (onion) ^b	Plant in wide ridges No spraying difficulty Pest resistant crops UV-light protection onions	Chemical protection of onions excluded
Soil quality improvement	Intercropping with legumes Light machinery	Cover crops excluded. Only binary variable included.
Sprout prevention	Application of sprout inhibitor Mechanic cooling of potatoes	Separate for seed potato and ware and starch potato. Only binary variable included.
Water availability	Increase water storage Water-conserving soil tillage	NA

Note: No categories for drought adaptation or pest prevention for potato crops were tested in the regressions, as measures that were part of these categories were adopted >85 %. ^a The variables traditional drainage, cover crops, chemical protection were excluded since these variables were adopted by >85 % of respondents. ^b For these categories, the individual variables (except drip irrigation and UV-light protection) were also included separately in the regression models to test if that improved model fit more than the composite indicator, since the adoption of drip irrigation and UV-light protection was less than 10 %.

Fig. B1. Share of farmers who adopted at least one measure in one of the larger adaptation strategy categories.

Appendix C. Extreme weather event occurrence

There were many extreme weather events from 2018 to 2022 (Tables C1 and C2), with strong differences over time and spatially. In 2018, the extremes wet field during plowing, dry summer, and heatwave occurred in most of the country, and had the highest intensity compared to the other extremes. The extremes that were most pronounced in 2019 were wet field during harvest and for seed onions, a dry summer, extreme heat, and heatwaves. This was the only year in which the extreme ‘extreme heat’ (temperature above 40 °C for at least two consecutive days) occurred. In 2020, there were the most different types of extremes with a high intensity and frequency: wet field during harvest, plowing and for seed onions, prolonged wet period for seed potato, extreme rain for potatoes, heatwaves, and a dry spring. In 2021, the extremes prolonged wet for ware & starch potato, extreme rainfall onion and potato were the most pronounced. This was the only year where no heatwaves occurred at any temperature station in the country. The year 2022 was characterized by a warm winter, dry summer, and dry spring. Late frost did not occur in all five years. There was not a large difference in warm and wet period intensity during the study period (Table C2).

Heatwaves and warm winters occurred significantly more further away from the coastline (Table C3). Prolonged wet period during the ware and starch potato vulnerable period occurred the least very close to the coast, but there was no clear spatial pattern beyond that (Table C3). The occurrence of extremes was higher near the coast for the extremes wet fields during harvesting, plowing and during the vulnerable period of seed onions, extreme rainfall affecting potatoes, as well as the prolonged wet period during the vulnerable period of seed potatoes. For the drought, extreme rainfall affecting onions, warm and wet periods there is no clear spatial pattern based on coastal distance.

Table C1

Comparison of mean precipitation-related extreme weather event occurrence during the years 2018–2022, and the spatial coverage of the extreme event over time.

Year	Prolonged wet period		Wet field			Extreme rainfall		Drought	
	Seed potato	Ware & starch potato	Harvesting (potato)	Plowing (potato)	Seed onion	Potato	Seed onion	Spring	Summer
Mean frequency¹									
2018	0.00 ^a	0.00 ^a	0.00 ^a	14.64 ^a	0.11 ^a	0.33 ^a	0.03 ^a	3.66 ^a	28.17 ^a
2019	0.01 ^a	0.02 ^a	14.20 ^b	6.34 ^b	0.79 ^b	0.25 ^a	0.03 ^a	4.82 ^b	9.30 ^b
2020	1.24 ^b	0.21 ^a	5.72 ^c	30.65 ^c	0.56 ^b	0.59 ^b	0.05 ^a	19.10 ^c	0.79 ^c
2021	0.04 ^a	3.55 ^b	0.03 ^a	9.11 ^d	0.08 ^a	1.00 ^c	0.17 ^b	0.94 ^d	0.81 ^c
2022	0.21 ^a	0.00 ^a	0.28 ^a	7.59 ^{bd}	0.24 ^a	0.45 ^{ab}	0.02 ^a	6.46 ^e	2.90 ^d
Share of precipitation station (%)¹									
2018	0.0	0.0	0.0	90.1	2.6	15.7	3.2	42.9	99.7
2019	1.0	1.3	98.4	86.5	20.2	16.7	2.6	50.3	72.4
2020	29.8	9.3	78.2	100.0	10.3	23.4	5.1	100.0	35.9
2021	1.9	47.8	1.6	84.9	5.4	40.1	15.1	13.5	15.4
2022	5.1	0.0	7.4	77.6	5.8	20.8	1.9	97.4	69.2

¹Based on 312 precipitation stations.

Superscript letters indicate significant differences per column. Means in the same column with the same lower-case superscript letters are not significantly different ($\alpha = 0.05$) according to a post-hoc Tukey HSD test.

Table C2

Comparison of mean temperature-related extreme weather event occurrence during the years 2018–2022, and the spatial coverage of the extreme event over time.

Year	Heatwave	Late frost	Warm winter	Warm and wet period potato	Warm and wet period seed onion	Extreme heat
Mean frequency						
2018	6.12 ^a	0.00 ^a	0.00 ^a	0.35 ^{ab}	0.35 ^{ab}	0.00 ^a
2019	4.21 ^{ab}	0.00 ^a	0.91 ^a	0.88 ^{ab}	0.85 ^{ab}	0.26 ^b
2020	6.09 ^a	0.00 ^a	0.00 ^a	1.24 ^a	1.21 ^a	0.00 ^a
2021	0.00 ^c	0.00 ^a	0.09 ^a	0.65 ^{ab}	0.65 ^{ab}	0.00 ^a
2022	3.59 ^b	0.00 ^a	3.24 ^b	0.03 ^b	0.00 ^b	0.00 ^a
Share of temperature stations (%)¹						
2018	76.5	0.0	0.0	8.8	8.8	0.0
2019	100.0	0.0	38.2	26.5	29.4	26.5
2020	91.2	0.0	0.0	38.2	41.2	0.0
2021	0.0	0.0	2.9	11.8	11.8	0.0
2022	85.3	0.0	38.2	0.0	2.9	0.0

¹Based on 34 temperature stations.Superscript letters indicate significant differences per column. Means in the same column with the same lower-case superscript letters are not significantly different ($\alpha = 0.05$) according to a post-hoc Tukey HSD test.**Table C3**

Effect of distance to the coast on the mean occurrence of precipitation and temperature extremes between 2018 and 2022 in the Netherlands.

Distance to coastline	Prolonged wet period		Wet field			Extreme rainfall		Temperature extremes	
	Seed potato	Ware & starch potato	Harvesting (potato)	Plowing (potato)	Seed onion	Potato	Seed onion ¹	Heatwave	Warm winter
0–25 km	0.51 ^a	0.33 ^a	5.41 ^a	17.70 ^a	0.86 ^a	0.76 ^a	0.04 ^a	2.02 ^a	0.29 ^a
25–50 km	0.35 ^{ab}	0.86 ^b	4.10 ^b	14.50 ^b	0.30 ^b	0.49 ^b	0.05 ^{ab}	4.00 ^b	0.93 ^{ab}
50–100 km	0.23 ^b	1.14 ^b	3.65 ^{bc}	12.40 ^b	0.16 ^{bc}	0.42 ^b	0.08 ^b	4.83 ^{bc}	0.57 ^{ab}
100–200 km	0.08 ^b	0.73 ^{ab}	2.77 ^c	9.37 ^c	0.01 ^c	0.38 ^b	0.07 ^{ab}	6.50 ^c	1.92 ^b

Only extremes with significant effects are included in the table based on a two-way ANOVA test. Superscript letters indicate significant differences per column. Means in the same column with the same lower-case superscript letters are not significantly different ($\alpha = 0.05$) according to a post-hoc Tukey HSD test. ¹ Only significant at $\alpha = 0.10$.

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